

Web-Based Strategic Performance Management System for President Ramon Magsaysay State University

Carl Angelo S. Pamplona, Menchie A. Dela Cruz

College of Communication and Information Technology President Ramon Magsaysay State University Zambales, Philippines

Abstract- The web-based strategic performance management system for President Ramon Magsaysay State University (PRMSU) was developed to provide a more streamlined and centralized way of handling performance management-related tasks. The main purpose of the study was to evaluate the developed system in terms of software quality (using ISO/IEC 25010:2011 metrics), level of acceptability, and level of readiness of PRMSU. The study also identified significant differences between the evaluations of PRMSU staff and supervisors on (a) software quality of the system, (b) acceptability of functionality and performance, and (c) readiness for implementation in terms of information system facility and technical personnel. Based on the respondents' evaluation, the developed system's software quality was "Excellent," its level of acceptability was "Highly Acceptable," and its readiness for implementation was "Very Ready." There was no significant difference between staff and supervisor evaluations on software quality or on any of the measured domains (Functional Suitability, Performance Efficiency, Compatibility, Usability, Reliability, Security, Maintainability, and Portability). Finally, the researcher provided recommendations including full implementation of the system, periodic re-evaluation and maintenance, user training, and ongoing studies to align with evolving trends such as implementation of data analytics and artificial intelligence functionalities.

Keywords – Web-Based System; Strategic Performance Management; Software Quality; ISO/IEC 25010; Acceptability; Readiness.

I. INTRODUCTION

Documents, whether electronic or paper, are essential in any organization, and managing data from multiple sources can be challenging. While centralized document management systems can collect, store, and retrieve documents efficiently, many institutions still rely on fragmented or partially digital systems, creating inefficiencies and potential data loss. Centralized access to documents improves productivity by making business and client information readily available to stakeholders, whereas physical paper is prone to misplacement or duplication. Despite the clear advantages of automation and centralization, many organizations have not fully implemented systems that integrate workflow, document tracking, and performance management, leaving gaps in operational efficiency. Centralized systems also reduce costs by automating repetitive tasks, including performance management-related recordkeeping, which remains largely manual in some institutions.

Performance management is a collaborative process where employees and management plan, monitor, and review performance continuously. In educational institutions, implementing and improving the Strategic Performance Management System (SPMS) is challenging, particularly due

to reliance on manual processes and inconsistent recordkeeping. In the Philippines, SPMS links employee performance with organizational outcomes to enhance compensation systems and ensure objectives are met (Civil

Service Commission, 2012). Traditionally, SPMS relied on Individual Performance Commitment and Review Form (IPCRF) and Office Performance Commitment and Review Form (OPCRF) which are time-consuming, prone to errors, and often duplicated. Although PRMSU implemented an Electronic Individual Performance Commitment and Review (e-IPCR) system across its campuses in 2021, offline and physical copies still exist, creating inefficiencies and risk of lost data. Dela Cruz (2018) emphasized the need for a centralized system to manage faculty performance evaluation; however, previous implementations have not fully automated workflow or integrated evaluation evidence, representing a clear gap in current SPMS practices.

Based on these gaps, this study developed and evaluated a Web-Based Strategic Performance Management System for PRMSU Main Campus, providing a centralized platform for performance management documents and an automated ratings system. By streamlining workflows, the system aims to enhance productivity and efficiency, addressing the lack of integrated, automated SPMS solutions observed in existing

literature. The objectives were to design and implement the system and evaluate it in terms of software quality (ISO/IEC 25010:2011), acceptability, and readiness for implementation. The study benefits university administrators by enabling faster, data-driven decision-making and improving document processing efficiency; college deans by streamlining SPMS document processing and ratings; faculty by facilitating submission of performance documents and evidence; staff by enhancing operational efficiency; students indirectly through more faculty engagement; and future researchers as a foundation for SPMS improvement or similar system development.

This study specifically evaluated software quality using ISO/IEC 25010:2011 metrics, including Functional Suitability, Performance Efficiency, Compatibility, Usability, Reliability, Security, Maintainability, and Portability. It assessed acceptability in terms of functionality and performance and readiness based on information system facilities and technical personnel. Differences between staff and supervisor respondents in software quality, acceptability, and readiness were also examined. The scope included the design, development, testing, and evaluation of a web-based SPMS for PRMSU, featuring automated workflows for IPCRF and OPCRF processing by deans and faculty.

Developed using PHP and Bootstrap, the system supports multiple devices via web browsers and requires Internet access. It features two user types: administrators, who manage users, settings, and reports, and regular users (staff and supervisors), who can submit forms, upload evidence, and generate reports. The system is limited to PRMSU Main Campus. The Rapid Application Development (RAD) methodology guided development with iterative prototyping and user feedback. Data was collected using survey questionnaires and analyzed through descriptive and inferential statistics, including percentage, mean, t-test, and ANOVA, addressing the literature gap on evaluating web-based SPMS with standardized software quality metrics.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Performance management is a continuous effort to improve organizational outcomes by setting individual and team goals aligned with strategic objectives, planning performance to achieve these goals, reviewing progress, and developing the knowledge, skills, and abilities of personnel (Armstrong, 2018). Typically, this involves structured procedures for planning, monitoring, and reviewing performance. The Strategic Performance Management System (SPMS) connects employee and organizational performance to enhance the compensation system's performance orientation. By aligning objectives with the Philippine Development Plan, Agency Strategic Plan, and Organizational Performance Indicator Framework, SPMS aims to improve both organizational and

individual effectiveness. Key components include goals, output/outcomes orientation, team approaches, user-friendly forms, information systems, and communication plans. SPMS complements the Results-Based Performance Management System and is integrated with the Performance-Based Incentive System (PBIS), following a four-stage cycle: performance planning and commitment, monitoring and coaching, review and evaluation, and rewarding and development planning, using a five-point rating scale from Outstanding to Poor (Civil Service Commission, 2012). However, despite these established structures, gaps persist in implementing real-time monitoring, automated feedback, and adaptive reporting across diverse units, which can delay performance assessment and reduce consistency in evaluation outcomes.

Electronic systems have become essential for fast and efficient transactions in organizations, supporting quality output across businesses, society, and educational institutions. Studies evaluating electronic Individual Performance Commitment and Review (e-IPCR) systems, such as those at Ramon Magsaysay Technological University Zambales (RMTU), assessed effectiveness, user acceptability, and potential enhancements. Using causal comparative descriptive research, respondents included college deans and faculty, selected via purposive sampling. The DeLone and McLean Success Model measured information quality, system quality, service quality, intention to use, user satisfaction, and net benefits. Results indicated that the e-IPCR system was "Effective" and that user acceptability for continual adoption was "Acceptable," with LAN-based databases ranked as the preferred integration (Dela Cruz, 2018). Yet, gaps remain in scalability, cloud integration, and remote access, suggesting that while systems perform well in controlled settings, broader organizational adoption may face unforeseen challenges.

Effective performance management integrates both human and technological mechanisms. Human processes involve regular check-ins, feedback discussions, and proactive problem-solving, while technological tools track metrics, identify bottlenecks, and facilitate data-driven decisions (Couwenbergh, 2021). Nevertheless, organizations often struggle to balance software sophistication with usability, indicating a gap in creating systems that are simultaneously intuitive, scalable, and capable of predictive analytics (Hazen et al., 2014).

Management innovations (MIs) influence organizational performance directly and indirectly through performance management, yet their effects remain under-explored in public contexts (Walker, Damanpour & Devece, 2011). Van Dooren (2014) highlights that New Public Management spurred government performance management reforms, but limitations in agility, decentralization, and political navigation suggest gaps in current frameworks. Similarly, Resurreccion (2012) shows that Filipino SMEs face challenges from traditional

bureaucratic structures and globalization pressures, pointing to a gap in understanding how performance management practices can enhance competitiveness under changing economic conditions.

In educational settings, evaluations of the School Monitoring, Evaluation and Adjustment (SMEA) System identified high implementation levels, but qualitative findings exposed gaps in indicator validity, reliability, and contextual adaptation (Paragoso & Barazon, 2019). Strategic performance measurement systems (SPMS) can influence employee behavior and motivation, yet their effectiveness varies with age, education, and organizational climate, indicating gaps in universal applicability (Burney & Widener, 2013). Bento, Bento, and White (2014) further demonstrate that SPMS IT and system design variables affect business outcomes, but research is limited on cross-industry applicability, highlighting a gap in external validity.

Although the Balanced Scorecard (Kaplan & Norton, 1992) and subsequent SPMS studies show positive impacts on organizational capabilities and performance, substantial heterogeneity exists due to national culture, industry differences, and reward-system integration (Endrikat, Guenther & Titus, 2020). Similarly, Perez (2014) points out gaps in SPMS adaptability in highly dynamic environments. Slovak industries demonstrate benefits of strategic business performance management alongside financial metrics, yet gaps remain in universally applying modern management concepts (Zamecnik & Rajnoha, 2015). Performance appraisals provide employees clarity and motivation, yet gaps persist in linking appraisal results to long-term career development and evolving organizational objectives (Ahmed, 2020). The COVID-19 pandemic has further revealed gaps in virtual work management, requiring agile leadership and digital readiness (Bartsch et al., 2020; Savić, 2020).

Web-based systems and applications, including Web-Based Support Systems (WSS) and Software as a Service (SaaS), offer flexibility, scalability, and efficiency, allowing organizations to reduce costs, improve productivity, enhance security, and maintain continuity (Sturm, Pollard & Craig, 2017; Khanna, 2019; De Vos, 2017; Laidre, 2011; Khamooshi, 2019). However, gaps remain in infrastructure readiness, user training, and integration with legacy systems, particularly in public institutions and educational settings where technical preparedness varies.

Studies highlight that web-based performance management systems improve efficiency and accuracy. In the Philippines, Dizon et al. (2018) noted that periodic evaluations and adherence to RPMS guidelines are critical for effectiveness. In UAE federal organizations, E-PMS enhanced operational efficiency and employee performance monitoring, but gaps persist in transitioning from manual systems and in user

adaptation (Al-Raisi, Amin & Tahir, 2010). Dela Cruz (2018) similarly noted that while e-IPCR systems facilitate efficiency and user acceptability, broader access and feature integration are needed. Alshowair and Alkhatabi (2015) and Ullah et al. (2021) found that web-based appraisal tools improve perceived accuracy and motivation, yet gaps remain in mitigating burnout, turnover, and uneven digital literacy among users.

The COVID-19 pandemic accelerated reliance on remote performance management, emphasizing digital readiness, leadership adaptability, and resilient IT infrastructure (Bartsch et al., 2020; Savić, 2020; Whitelaw et al., 2020). These studies collectively reveal persistent gaps in integrating technological, human, and organizational elements for performance management, underscoring the necessity for continuous innovation, evaluation, and alignment with both strategic objectives and dynamic operational contexts.

The reviewed literature underscores the critical role of performance management systems in improving organizational effectiveness, employee motivation, and decision-making processes. Studies consistently demonstrate that strategic alignment, robust information systems, and web-based technologies enhance both operational efficiency and user satisfaction (Armstrong, 2018; Dela Cruz, 2018; Couwenbergh, 2021; Al-Raisi, Amin & Tahir, 2010). However, persistent gaps remain in adaptability, scalability, and integration with legacy systems, especially in public and educational institutions. These gaps highlight the need for systematic evaluation frameworks capable of addressing both technical and human factors in system adoption.

To address these gaps, the researcher adopted the ISO/IEC 25010:2011 software quality model as the primary evaluative framework. This model, classified as a product quality model, comprises of eight characteristics namely functional suitability, performance efficiency, compatibility, usability, reliability, security, maintainability, and portability with each subdivided into sub-characteristics representing static software properties and dynamic system behavior. By modifying the model to suit the context of the Web-based Strategic Performance Management System (SPMS) for President Ramon Magsaysay State University Main Campus, the study enables a comprehensive assessment of software quality that incorporates both technical performance and user-centric considerations.

The study's conceptual framework employs the Input- Process-Output (IPO) model. The input consists of the developed Web-based SPMS, while the process entails evaluation using ISO/IEC 25010:2011, assessment of level of acceptability, determination of the level of readiness, and systematic collection and analysis of survey data. The output includes the evaluated software quality, the acceptability of continuous adoption among respondents, and the level of readiness to

implement the system. Feedback from staff and supervisors will inform future enhancements, ensuring that the system remains responsive to organizational and user needs.

The study also tests six null hypotheses addressing differences in software evaluation, acceptability, and readiness between staff and supervisor respondents and across specific domain groupings. Testing these hypotheses not only measures the effectiveness and usability of the system but also identifies domain-specific areas where additional training or system adjustments may be necessary. By integrating rigorous software quality assessment with user acceptability and readiness evaluation, the study fills a notable gap in prior research: providing a systematic, empirical foundation for adopting web-based performance management systems in higher education institutions.

III. METHODOLOGY

This study used a combination of descriptive and analytical research design. Descriptive research allowed investigation of specific subjects and provided groundwork for quantitative analysis (Shuttleworth, 2008). The software development approach was based on the Rapid Application Development (RAD) model. RAD emphasizes quick, iterative prototyping, focusing on adaptability and customer satisfaction. It is designed to be flexible to change and input at every step of development, sacrificing some adherence to fixed deadlines for the sake of quality and responsiveness. Rapid development reduces time and cost but requires careful management of scope and testing.

The study was conducted at PRMSU Main Campus, Iba, Zambales and study's respondents were the supervisors (college deans) and staff (faculty) at PRMSU Iba-Main Campus. The target population included all college deans (10) and faculty (284) at the main campus. Using purposive sampling, 8 supervisors (80%) and 100 staff (35.2%) participated, for a total sample of 108 (36.73% of the population). Table 1 shows the frequency and percentage distribution:

Table 1: Frequency and Percentage Distribution of Staff and Supervisor-respondents

Respondent	Population Frame	Sample Frame	Sample Percentage
Supervisor	10	8	80.00%
Staff	284	100	35.20%
TOTAL	294	108	36.73%

The main instrument was a survey questionnaire, an appropriate tool for descriptive research. The questionnaire was structured in parts: Part I collected respondent profile (identifying respondent type: Staff or Supervisor). Part II

assessed software quality of the Web-based SPMS using ISO/IEC 25010:2011 metrics (31 items, using a 4-point scale: 4 = Excellent (E), 3 = Good (G), 2 = Below Average (BA), 1 = Poor (P)). Part III measured level of acceptability for continued system use (6 items on Functionality and Performance, 4-point scale: 4 = Highly Acceptable (HA), 3 = Acceptable (A), 2 = Slightly Acceptable (SA), 1 = Not Acceptable (NA)). Part IV measured level of readiness for implementation (6 items on Information System Facility and Technical Personnel, 4-point scale: 4 = Very Ready (VR), 3 = Ready (R), 2 = Slightly Ready (SR), 1 = Not Ready (NR)). The questionnaire's content was based on ISO/IEC 25010:2011 (Systems and Software Quality Requirements and Evaluation) and was validated by research experts.

Data was collected by administering the questionnaire and demonstrating the system to respondents at PRMSU Main Campus. An online method was used where the questionnaire was distributed via Google Forms to the 100 staff (faculty) and 8 supervisors (deans). A purposive sampling technique was used for targeting relevant respondents.

The collected data were systematically tabulated and analyzed using Microsoft Excel. To summarize the distribution of responses, frequency distribution was employed, providing an overview of how respondents' evaluations were spread across different values. The mean was calculated to determine the average ratings of respondents on software quality, evaluated across the ISO/IEC 25010:2011 quality characteristics, as well as the levels of acceptability (Functionality, Performance) and readiness (Facility, Personnel). Percentages were used to determine the proportion of respondents falling into specific categories, while ranking enabled the ordering of items relative to each other, such as prioritizing software quality metrics according to their weighted means.

For qualitative interpretation, the Likert scale was used with specific intervals assigned for each measured dimension. Software quality ratings were interpreted as Excellent (3.25–4.00), Good (2.50–3.24), Average (1.75–2.49), and Poor (1.00–1.74). Acceptability ratings were classified as Highly Acceptable (3.25–4.00), Acceptable (2.50–3.24), Moderately Acceptable (1.75–2.49), and Unacceptable (1.00–1.74). Readiness levels were interpreted as Very Ready (3.25–4.00), Ready (2.50–3.24), Moderately Ready (1.75–2.49), and Not Ready (1.00–1.74).

To determine whether significant differences existed between groups, independent-samples t-tests were conducted to compare the mean evaluations of staff and supervisor respondents. The decision rule involved comparing the calculated t-statistic with the t-critical value: if the t-statistic was less than the t-critical value, the null hypothesis of no significant difference was accepted; if it exceeded the t-critical value, the null hypothesis was rejected, indicating a statistically

significant difference between the groups. For comparisons involving more than two groups or domains, single-factor Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) was employed. The resulting F-statistic from ANOVA was compared against the F-critical value to test the null hypothesis that all group means were equal, with rejection of the null hypothesis occurring when the F- statistic exceeded the F-critical value, thereby identifying statistically significant differences across the examined groups or domains.

This combination of descriptive and inferential statistical tools provided a thorough and systematic evaluation of the Web-based Strategic Performance Management System, enabling detailed insights into software quality, user acceptability, and institutional readiness, while also highlighting significant differences across user groups and operational domains.

Table 2. Evaluation of Software Quality of Web-based Strategic Performance Management System as evaluated by PRMSU Staff and Supervisor Respondent using ISO/IEC 25010:2011 metrics

ISO/IEC 25010:2011 METRICS	PRMSU Staff			PRMSU Supervisor		
	WM	DE	Rank	WM	DE	Rank
Functional Suitability	3.64	Excellent	3	3.54	Excellent	4.5
Performance Efficiency	3.67	Excellent	1	3.50	Excellent	7.5
Compatibility	3.62	Excellent	5.5	3.56	Excellent	2
Usability	3.65	Excellent	2	3.50	Excellent	7.5
Reliability	3.61	Excellent	7.5	3.53	Excellent	6
Security	3.61	Excellent	7.5	3.58	Excellent	1
Maintainability	3.64	Excellent	4	3.55	Excellent	3
Portability	3.62	Excellent	5.5	3.54	Excellent	4.5
Grand Mean	3.63	Excellent		3.54	Excellent	

Table 3. Evaluation of Level of Acceptability of Web-based Strategic Performance Management System as evaluated by

Criteria	PRMSU Staff			PRMSU Supervisor		
	WM	DE	Rank	WM	DE	Rank
Functionality	3.60	Highly Acceptable	2	3.50	Highly Acceptable	2
Performance	3.61	Highly Acceptable	1	3.54	Highly Acceptable	1
Grand Mean	3.60	Highly Acceptable		3.52	Highly Acceptable	

Table 4. Evaluation of Level of Readiness for Implementation of Web-based Strategic Performance Management System as evaluated by PRMSU Staff and Supervisor Respondents

Criteria	PRMSU Staff			PRMSU Supervisor		
	WM	DE	Rank	WM	DE	Rank
Information System Facility	3.48	Very Ready	1	3.75	Very Ready	1
Technical Personnel	3.46	Very Ready	2	3.67	Very Ready	2
Grand Mean	3.47	Very Ready		3.71	Very Ready	

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Software Quality as to ISO/IEC 25010:2011 Metrics

Table 2 shows respondents' evaluation of Functional Suitability. The evaluation of the Web-based Strategic Performance Management System by PRMSU staff and supervisor respondents reveals consistently high perceptions across all measured software quality metrics, reflecting the system's robustness and alignment with institutional needs. Among staff respondents, Performance Efficiency received the highest weighted mean of 3.67, interpreted as "Excellent,"

indicating that the system efficiently supports task completion, resource utilization, and overall performance monitoring. In contrast, Reliability and Security received slightly lower weighted means of 3.61, yet still "Excellent," suggesting that while the system is dependable and secure, minor opportunities may exist for improving fail-safes or security protocols. The overall grand mean of 3.63 confirms that staff perceive the software quality of the system as excellent, emphasizing its functional suitability and effectiveness in daily operational use.

Supervisor respondents similarly rated the system highly, with Security achieving the top weighted mean of 3.58 ("Excellent"), highlighting the importance supervisors place on safeguarding sensitive institutional data and ensuring

compliance with access control measures. Performance Efficiency and Usability were rated slightly lower at 3.50, yet still within the “Excellent” range, reflecting that supervisors perceive the system as functional but potentially benefiting from minor usability enhancements to facilitate navigation and operational efficiency. The grand mean of 3.54 underscores that supervisors generally perceive the software quality as excellent, reinforcing confidence in the system’s ability to meet organizational objectives.

The slight differences in metric prioritization between staff and supervisors suggest divergent perspectives influenced by role-specific responsibilities. Staff appear to value efficiency in completing tasks, while supervisors emphasize data security and oversight. These findings align with the principles of ISO/IEC 25010:2011, which posit that software quality encompasses multiple interrelated characteristics, all of which contribute to the perceived effectiveness and reliability of the system. Overall, the results indicate a high level of acceptance and satisfaction with the Web-based Strategic Performance Management System, while signaling potential areas for incremental improvement in reliability, usability, and security to further enhance user experience and institutional readiness.

Level of Acceptability

Table 3 shows the evaluation of Level of Acceptability of Web-based Strategic Performance Management System as evaluated by PRMSU Staff and Supervisor Respondents. The results show that both staff and supervisors view the system as performing well in the areas of functionality and performance, with all ratings falling within the “Highly Acceptable” range. Staff placed slightly greater emphasis on performance, giving it the highest overall mean of 3.61, while functionality followed with 3.60.

This pattern suggests that staff value smooth system operation and responsiveness because these directly support their routine documentation and reporting tasks. Supervisors reflected a similar trend by rating performance highest at 3.54, followed by functionality at 3.50, indicating that they appreciate how the system streamlines oversight activities but may still foresee minor refinements that can strengthen functional support for managerial tasks. The grand means of 3.60 for staff and 3.52 for supervisors reinforce the shared view that the system works well for its intended purpose and is acceptable for continued institutional use.

These findings echo earlier evidence showing that user acceptance improves when systems support task clarity and reduce effort, as highlighted by Scholtz, Mahmud, and Ramayah (2016), who reported that interface usability shapes perceptions of usefulness and ease of use, ultimately

influencing intention to use. This connection is relevant because both staff and supervisors gave consistently high scores across acceptability indicators, indicating that the system’s interface and functions

already support positive user attitudes. Despite these strong results, the small score differences between groups also point to a need for ongoing refinement, particularly in areas that improve workflow support for supervisory functions.

Level of Readiness for Implementation

The readiness results indicate that both staff and supervisors regard the university as well-positioned to fully implement the Web-based Strategic Performance Management System. Staff rated the Information System Facility highest with an overall mean of 3.48, followed closely by Technical Personnel at 3.46, both interpreted as “Very Ready,” leading to an overall readiness mean of 3.47.

These ratings reflect confidence in the institution’s existing infrastructure and its capacity to support continuous system operation. Supervisors provided even higher assessments, giving 3.75 for Information System Facility and 3.67 for Technical Personnel, likewise categorized as “Very Ready.” Their perspective suggests strong assurance that the current network, hardware support, and administrative capabilities can sustain institutional deployment. The close alignment between staff and supervisory scores indicates shared recognition that the university already maintains the essential foundation required for stable implementation. This is consistent with Firesmith (2012), who emphasized that strong infrastructure and proactive preparation are critical because addressing weaknesses only after vulnerabilities appear often leads to higher operational risk.

The findings also relate to Aggarwal (2002), who noted that long-term system upkeep demands clear documentation and stable technical capability, underscoring the importance of personnel readiness as systems mature. While the results point to a high level of assurance across both evaluation groups, the slight score differences suggest that strengthening documentation practices and ongoing technical training can support smoother maintenance and long-term system continuity.

Significant Differences

The t-test results in Table 5 show that all indicators recorded values lower than the t-critical threshold, which leads to the acceptance of the null hypothesis. This means that staff and supervisors provided comparable evaluations across Functional Suitability, Performance Efficiency, Compatibility, Usability, Reliability, Security,

Table 5. t-Computed Value on Software Quality
of the Web-based Strategic Performance Management System

Independent Sample T-test						
Domain	Mean		df	t-Stat	T Critical two-tail	Hypothesis
	Staff	Supervisor				
Functional Suitability	3.64	3.54	106	0.47	1.98	Not Significant, Accept Ho
Performance Efficiency	3.67	3.50	106	0.87	1.98	Not Significant, Accept Ho
Compatibility	3.62	3.56	106	0.28	1.98	Not Significant, Accept Ho
Usability	3.65	3.50	106	0.75	1.98	Not Significant, Accept Ho
Reliability	3.61	3.53	106	0.36	1.98	Not Significant, Accept Ho
Security	3.61	3.58	106	0.17	1.98	Not Significant, Accept Ho
Maintainability	3.64	3.55	106	0.37	1.98	Not Significant, Accept Ho
Portability	3.62	3.54	106	0.40	1.98	Not Significant, Accept Ho

Table 6. Analysis of Variance to Test Difference on the Software Quality Evaluation of PRMSU Staff- respondents according to domains

Domain	Count	Sum	Average	Variance		
Functional Suitability	100	363.67	3.64	0.309977553		
Performance Efficiency	100	366.67	3.67	0.271604938		
Compatibility	100	362	3.62	0.313737374		
Usability	100	365	3.65	0.297138047		
Reliability	100	361	3.61	0.353939394		
Maintainability	100	361.2	3.61	0.35460202		
Portability	100	363.6	3.64	0.330812121		
Security	100	362	3.62	0.334500561		
Source of Variation	SS	df	MS	F	P-value	F crit
Between Groups	0.273283	7	0.03904	0.121701	0.9968	2.02112
Within Groups	254.0648	792	0.320789			
Total	254.33	799				

Decision: Accept Null Hypothesis (Not Significant)

Table 7. Analysis of Variance to Test Difference on the Software Quality Evaluation of PRMSU Supervisor- respondents according to domains

Domain	Count	Sum	Average	Variance		
Functional Suitability	8	28.33	3.54	0.188492063		
Performance Efficiency	8	28	3.5	0.253968254		
Compatibility	8	28.5	3.56	0.245535714		
Usability	8	28	3.5	0.174603175		
Reliability	8	28.25	3.53	0.204241071		
Maintainability	8	28.6	3.58	0.210714286		
Portability	8	28.4	3.55	0.34		
Security	8	28.33	3.54	0.283730159		
Source of Variation	SS	df	MS	F	P-value	F crit
Between Groups	0.04058	7	0.00579	0.024396	0.9999	2.17815
Within Groups	13.3089	56	0.23766			
Total	13.34	63				

Decision: Accept Null Hypothesis (Not Significant)

Maintainability, and Portability. Their consistent ratings suggest that both groups share similar experiences with the system's functions and perceive its performance in a uniform manner. This outcome indicates that the system delivers a stable level of quality regardless of the user's role in the institution. Gorla (2010) noted that organizational conditions often shape users' assessments of software, influencing attributes such as reliability, ease of use, and usefulness. The alignment between staff and supervisor evaluations in the present study reflects this observation, as both groups operate within the same institutional setting and interact with similar administrative workflows. While Gorla highlighted that differing perspectives can sometimes lead to varied assessments, the current findings show that PRMSU users view the system consistently, suggesting that the implementation supports shared expectations across job categories.

The ANOVA results shown in table 6 show that there is no significant difference in staff respondents' evaluation of the system across the domains of Functional Suitability, Performance Efficiency, Compatibility, Usability, Reliability, Security, Maintainability, and Portability. The computed F value of 0.121701 is less than the F critical value of 2.021123, leading to the acceptance of the null hypothesis. This indicates that staff evaluated all software quality domains consistently and viewed each as contributing equally to the system's overall performance. Such uniformity suggests that no single domain was perceived as notably stronger or weaker, reinforcing the idea that the system delivers balanced quality across its functions.

This outcome aligns with the position of Montagud, Abrahão, and Insfran (2012), who highlighted that user-perceived quality

emerges when software features match real user needs across both functional and non-functional areas. Their work emphasized that users increasingly expect software to provide stable performance, intuitive functions, and reliable operation, and that meeting these expectations improves satisfaction and strengthens overall product value. The consistent ratings from staff therefore imply that the system addresses core user requirements in a balanced manner, and that no domain requires disproportionate corrective attention at this stage.

The ANOVA results in Table 7 indicate that the supervisors' evaluations across the domains of Functional Suitability, Performance Efficiency, Compatibility, Usability, Reliability, Security, Maintainability, and Portability do not differ significantly. The computed F value of 0.024396098 is lower than the F critical value of 2.178155555, resulting in the acceptance of the null hypothesis. This shows that supervisors assessed all software quality domains in a consistent manner and attributed similar value to each metric in judging the overall quality of the system. Their uniform scoring suggests that the system delivers a steady level of operational performance meet their expectations to a comparable degree.

The pattern supports the findings of Mohamadali and Garibaldi (2011), who observed that different types of software may be influenced by distinct acceptance drivers, with performance expectancy demonstrating strong influence in research-focused systems and information quality in medical applications. In the present context, the uniform treatment of Functionality and Performance suggests that the system provides the key features staff consider important, resulting in aligned acceptance judgments across both domains.

Table 8. Analysis of Variance to Test Difference on the Level of Acceptability of PRMSU Staff- respondents according to domains

Domain		Count	Sum	Average	Variance	
Functionality		100	360	3.6	0.22222222	
Performance		100	361	3.61	0.224590348	
Source of Variation	SS	df	MS	F	P-value	F crit
Between Groups	0.005	1	0.005	0.02238	0.8812	3.88885
Within Groups	44.2344	198	0.2234			
Total	44.23	199				
Decision: Accept Null Hypothesis (Not Significant)						

Table 9. Analysis of Variance to Test Difference on the Level of Acceptability of PRMSU Supervisor- respondents according to domains

Domain		Count	Sum	Average	Variance	
Functionality		8	28	3.5	0.253968254	
Performance		8	28.33	3.54	0.251984127	
Source of Variation	SS	df	MS	F	P-value	F crit
Between Groups	0.00694	1	0.00694	0.02745	0.8707	4.60011
Within Groups	3.54166	14	0.25297			
Total	3.548	15				

Decision: Accept Null Hypothesis (Not Significant)

performance across its functions and that no domain was perceived as needing more attention than another. This pattern aligns with the findings of Hussain, Mkpojiogu, and Kutar (2019), who reported that users' perception of software performance is closely tied to the importance they assign to specific features. When the design includes features that users consider essential, their evaluations tend to reflect a positive and even distribution across quality elements. The consistency observed among PRMSU supervisors suggests that the system's design integrates the functions they consider important, resulting in balanced assessments across all domains.

The ANOVA results in Table 8 indicate that the staff's evaluations of the system's level of acceptability across the domains of Functionality and Performance do not differ significantly. The computed F value of 0.02238075 is lower than the F critical value of 3.888853, leading to the acceptance of the null hypothesis. This shows that staff respondents placed similar value on both domains when judging the system's acceptability, suggesting that their perception of the system's usefulness and suitability is stable across these areas. The consistency of ratings also indicates that the system's core functions and its

The ANOVA results shown in table 9 reveal that supervisors showed no significant difference in their evaluation of the system's acceptability across the domains of Functionality and Performance. The computed F value of 0.02745098 is lower than the F critical value of 4.60011, resulting in the acceptance of the null hypothesis. This indicates that supervisors assessed both domains with similar weight, suggesting that they view the

system's functional features and its operational performance as equally important in determining overall acceptability.

Their uniform scoring implies that the system delivers consistent value in both areas, without any domain standing out as weaker or stronger. This finding aligns with the study of Mlekus et al. (2020), which highlighted that user acceptance is shaped not only by traditional predictors but also by technology-specific qualities such as output quality, clarity, dependability, and novelty. When these characteristics are adequately addressed, employees tend to show balanced acceptance across various aspects of a system. The supervisors' consistent ratings suggest that these qualities may have been sufficiently met, leading to parallel judgments of Functionality and Performance.

The ANOVA results shown in table 10 show that staff respondents displayed no significant difference in their assessment of readiness across the domains of Information System Facility and Technical Personnel. The computed F value of 0.053631083 is lower than the F critical value of 3.88885, leading to the acceptance of the null hypothesis. This outcome indicates that staff members consistently Management System, covering both the Information System Facility and the Technical Personnel. Aziz and Yusof (2012) emphasized that successful organizational change relies on cooperation, commitment, and the ability of members to learn new methods that enhance service delivery. They noted that readiness is shaped by several factors, including leadership support, internal conditions, IT support, and the nature of the change itself. Their work highlights how strong readiness can strengthen implementation efforts and improve efficiency. However,

Table 10. Analysis of Variance to Test Difference on the Level of Readiness for Implementation of PRMSU Staff- respondents according to domains

Domain		Count	Sum	Average	Variance	
Information System Facility		100	348.33	3.48	0.377946128	
Technical Personnel		100	346.33	3.46	0.367890011	
Source of Variation	SS	df	MS	F	P-value	F crit
Between Groups	0.02	1	0.02	0.053631	0.8171	3.88885
Within Groups	73.83777	198	0.372918			
Total	73.857	199				

Decision: Accept Null Hypothesis (Not Significant)

Table 11. Analysis of Variance to Test Difference on the Level of Readiness for Implementation of PRMSU Supervisor- respondents according to domains

Domain		Count	Sum	Average	Variance	
Functionality		8	30	3.75	0.055555556	
Performance		8	29.33	3.67	0.19047619	
Source of Variation	SS	df	MS	F	P-value	F crit

Between Groups	0.02777	1	0.02777	0.225806	0.6419	4.60011
Within Groups	1.72222	14	0.12301			
Total	1.75	15				
Decision: Accept Null Hypothesis (Not Significant)						

viewed the university as prepared to implement the Web-based Strategic Performance Management System, with both infrastructure and personnel receiving comparable ratings. Their uniform evaluations suggest confidence in the institution's capability to support system deployment without any domain being perceived as a limiting factor. This pattern aligns with the findings of Esen and Özbağ (2014), who reported that organizational readiness positively influences perceived usefulness, perceived ease of use, and behavioral intention within e-HRM contexts. When readiness is evident across technical and human resources, users are more inclined to recognize the value of a digital system and express willingness to adopt it. The staff's consistent ratings reflect this relationship, indicating a stable foundation for implementation and a favorable environment for system uptake.

The results shown in Table 11 show no significant difference in the level of readiness when grouped by domains, as indicated by the computed F value of 0.225806452, which is lower than the F critical value of 4.60011. This leads to the acceptance of the null hypothesis. The finding indicates that PRMSU Supervisor- respondents consistently assessed President Ramon Magsaysay State University as ready for the implementation of the Web-based Strategic Performance their study concentrated on broad organizational-level change and did not examine readiness specific to performance management systems in public universities. This leaves a gap that the present research helps address by evaluating readiness within a specialized academic context and a specific digital system.

V. CONCLUSION

The study revealed that both staff and supervisor respondents consistently evaluated the Web-based Strategic Performance Management System of President Ramon Magsaysay State University Main Campus as excellent in terms of software quality. Performance efficiency and security were rated highest among the quality metrics, reflecting the system's robust functionality and reliability. Similarly, the level of acceptability was deemed highly acceptable across both respondent groups, with performance and functionality receiving the highest weighted means. The evaluation of institutional readiness showed that the university is very ready to implement the system, with both information system facilities and technical personnel adequately prepared. Statistical analyses, including t-tests and ANOVA, indicated no significant differences between staff and supervisor evaluations, nor among the different domains of software quality, acceptability, or readiness, demonstrating that respondents consistently

perceived the system's quality and institutional preparedness. These findings suggest that the Web-based Strategic Performance Management System is well-aligned with user expectations and organizational needs, supporting its adoption and operational use.

Based on these results, the study recommends the full implementation of the Web-based Strategic Performance Management System, accompanied by periodic re-evaluations to validate its continued effectiveness and user satisfaction. Regular maintenance should be conducted to ensure system reliability, and user training sessions are essential to facilitate smooth operation and maximize usability. Furthermore, ongoing studies are encouraged to keep the system aligned with evolving technological trends, including the integration of data analytics and artificial intelligence functionalities, which can enhance decision-making, performance monitoring, and overall institutional efficiency. These measures aim to strengthen system adoption, improve operational outcomes, and ensure that the university fully benefits from current and emerging advancements in performance management technologies.

REFERENCES

1. H. Abdel-Rahim and D. Stevens, "Information System Precision and Honesty in Managerial Reporting: A Re-Examination of Information Asymmetry Effects," *Accounting, Organizations and Society*, Vol. 64, 2018.
2. A. Ahmed, "The Effects of Performance Appraisals on Employees," *Small Business Chron*, 2020.
3. R. AlShowair and M. Alkhatabi, "Impact of a Web-Based Application for Employee Performance Management (EPMS) on Employee Performance: Employees' Opinions," *E-Article*, 2015.
4. A. Al-Raisi, S. Amin, and S. Tahir, "Effectiveness of Electronic Employee Performance Management Systems in the UAE Public Sector," *ResearchGate*, 2010.
5. A. Alzahrani, A. Alqazzaz, Y. Zhu, H. Fu, and N. Almarshfi, "Web Application Security Tools Analysis," *IEEE 3rd International Conference on Big Data Security on Cloud (BigDataSecurity), IEEE International Conference on High Performance and Smart Computing (HPSC), and IEEE International Conference on Intelligent Data and Security (IDS)*, pp. 237–242, 2017. doi: 10.1109/BigDataSecurity.2017.47.
6. M. Armstrong, *Handbook of Performance Management*, Kogan Page, 2017.

7. K. Aziz and M. M. Yusof, "Measuring Organizational Readiness in Information Systems Adoption," Americas Conference on Information Systems, 2012.
8. L. Barazon Jr. and S. Paragoso, "School Monitoring, Evaluation, and Adjustment (SMEA) in Central Cebu, Philippines," JHE CNU, 2019.
9. D. Barrett, "The Importance of Portability," Architect Blog, 2020.
10. S. Bartsch, E. Weber, M. Buttgen, and A. Huber, "Leadership Matters in Crisis-Induced Digital Transformation: How to Lead Service Employees Effectively During the COVID- 19 Pandemic," Emerald Insight, 2020.
11. L. Burney and S. Widener, "Behavioral Work Outcomes of a Strategic Performance Measurement System-Based Incentive Plan," BRIA, 25(2), 115–131, 2013.
12. A. Bento, R. Bento, and L. F. White, "Strategic Performance Management Systems: Impact on Business Results," Taylor & Francis, 2015.
13. R. Carpi, J. Douglas, and F. Gascon, "Performance Management: Why Keeping Score Is So Important, and So Hard," McKinsey Insights, 2017.
14. Civil Service Commission, "Strategic Performance Management System," CSC Philippines, 2012.
15. Civil Service Commission, "MC No. 6, s. 2012 - Guidelines in the Establishment and Implementation of Agency SPMS," CSC Philippines, 2012.
16. B. Cole, "What Is Software Usability?" Rocket Software Blog, 2014.
17. A. I. Cruz, "Web-based Supplies Monitoring and Inventory System (WEBMIS) using Forecasting Algorithm," 2020.
18. C. De Vos, "Legacy Apps: When to Modernize & Transition to Web-Based Apps?" Resolute TS, 2017.
19. M. Dela Cruz, "The Effectiveness of E-IPCR System as a Tool for Managing Faculty Performance Evaluation at the Ramon Magsaysay Technological University Main Campus Iba Zambales Philippines: A Basis for Enhancement," Granthaalayah Journal, 2018.
20. A. Dizon, A. San Pedro, M. Munsayac, and J. Padilla, "Level of Implementation of the Results-Based Performance Management System in the Department of Education Division of Gapan City, Philippines," ResearchGate, 2018.
21. J. Endrikat, T. Gunther, and R. Titus, "Consequences of Strategic Performance Measurement Systems: A Meta-Analytic Review," ResearchGate, 2019.
22. M. Esen and G. K. Özbağ, "An Investigation of the Effects of Organizational Readiness on Technology Acceptance in e- HRM Applications," International Journal of Human Resource Studies, 4(1), 2014.
23. N. Gorla and S. Lin, "Determinants of Software Quality: A Survey of Information Systems Project Managers," Information and Software Technology, 52(6), 602–610, 2010.
24. T. Hamilton, "Performance Testing Tutorial: What Is, Types, Metrics & Example," Guru99, 2021.
25. B. Hazen, C. Boone, J. Ezell, and A. Jones-Farmer, "Data Quality for Data Science, Predictive Analytics, and Big Data in Supply Chain Management: An Introduction to the Problem and Suggestions for Research and Applications," International Journal of Production Economics, 2014.
26. A. Hussain, E. O. C. Mkpojiogu, and M. Kutar, "The Impact of Software Features Perceived Importance on the Perceived Performance of Software Products Quality Elements," Journal of Computational and Theoretical Nanoscience, 16(5–6), 2135– 2140, 2019.
27. International Organization for Standardization, International Electrotechnical Commission, ISO/IEC 25010:2011 Systems and Software Engineering—Systems and Software Quality Requirements and Evaluation (SQuaRE)—System and Software Quality Models, 2017.
28. A. Kaley, "Match Between the System and the Real World: The 2nd Usability Heuristic Explained," NNGroup, 2018.
29. P. Khamooshi, "The Benefits of Using Web-Based Applications," 2019.
30. M. Khanna, "Why Web Applications Are Becoming Popular Than Standalone Applications?" 2019.
31. A. Laidre, "The Compelling Advantages of Web-Based Business Software," iPlanner, 2011.
32. R. Malhotra and A. Chug, "Software Maintainability: Systematic Literature Review and Current Trends," International Journal of Software Engineering and Knowledge Engineering, 26, 1221–1253, 2016.
33. L. Mlekus, D. Bentler, A. Paruzel, A.-L. Kato-Beiderwieden, and G. W. Maier, "How to Raise Technology Acceptance: User Experience Characteristics as Technology-Inherent Determinants," Gruppe. Interaktion. Organisation. Zeitschrift für Angewandte Organisationspsychologie (GIO), 51, 273–283, 2020.
34. N. A. Mohamadali and J. M. Garibaldi, "Comparing User Acceptance Factors Between Research Software and Medical Software Using AHP and Fuzzy AHP," 2011.
35. S. Montagud, S. Abrahão, and E. Insfran, "A Systematic Review of Quality Attributes and Measures for Software Product Lines," Software Quality Journal, 20(3), 425–486, 2012.
36. Nishadha, "Tech Talks ~ The Importance of Reliability," Creately Blog, 2011.
37. H. Perez, "The Influence of the Strategic Performance Measurement Systems (SPMS) on Business Decisions," Balas Conference Proceedings, 2014.
38. C. Poursaba, "The Top 7 Benefits of Document Management Systems," WhyMeridian, 2021.
39. P. Resurreccion, "Performance Management and Compensation as Drivers of Organization Competitiveness: The Philippine Perspective," IJBSSNet, 2012.

40. D. Savic, "COVID-19 and Work from Home: Digital Transformation of the Workforce," 2020.
41. M. Settle, "Information Technology – What Is It Good For?" CIO, 2019.
42. M. Shuttleworth, "Descriptive Research Design," Explorable, 2008.
43. R. Sturm, C. Pollard, and K. Craig, "Application Performance Management (APM) in the Digital Enterprise," ScienceDirect, 2017.
44. Z. Ullah, N. Ahmad, M. Scholz, B. Ahmed, I. Ahman, and M. Usman, "Perceived Accuracy of Electronic Performance Appraisal Systems: The Case of a Non-for-Profit Organization from an Emerging Economy," RePEc, 2021.
45. W. Van Dooren, "Better Performance Management," Taylor & Francis, 2014.
46. R. Walker, F. Damanpour, and C. Devece, "Management Innovation and Organizational Performance: The Mediating Effect of Performance Management," ResearchGate, 2011.
47. S. Whitelaw, M. Mamas, E. Topol, and H. Van Spall, "Applications of Digital Technology in COVID-19 Pandemic Planning and Response," The Lancet Digital Health, 2020.
48. J. Yao, "An Introduction to Web-Based Support System," De Gruyter, 2008.
49. R. Zamecnik and R. Rajnoha, "Strategic Business Performance Management on the Base of Controlling and Managerial Information Support," CORE, 2015.